

Information Access to Blind Persons in Cross River State: A Case Study of St. Joseph's Rehabilitation Centre

The study investigated the accessibility of blind students at St. Joseph's Rehabilitation Centre, Obudu, Cross-River State, to information sources needed for their education and personal development. A major finding was that these students relied more on personal contact for information than on printed sources or the library. It was postulated that materials provided were not tailored to the student's particular reading interests. Also, they were scantily available, and so, frequency of use was minimal. It was recommended that institutions and persons serving the blind in Nigerian should form a network on disability information issues such as collection development, resource-sharing and in in other countries.